

THE METHODOLOGY AND AVAILABILITY OF JOINT ICE CENTER SERVICES TO COMMERCIAL USERS

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Abstract

The data sources and methodology of producing sea and lake ice analysis and forecast products are examined. Remotely sensed data from National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), Defense Meteorological Satellite Program (DMSP), and National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) satellites are integrated with conventional ice information to construct operational ice analyses. Forecast guidance products from the Navy's Fleet Numerical Oceanography Center (FNOC) and NOAA's National Meteorological Center (NMC) are utilized in the production of ice forecast products. Ordering information and dissemination methods for ice services and products are identified.

1. Introduction

The Joint Ice Center (JIC) which is operated by NOAA and the U.S. Navy produces ice analysis and forecast products which are available to a broad group of commercial users. Existing commercial application of unrestricted government data and ice related services includes oil, marine transportation, aerospace engineering, environmental consulting, insurance underwriting, construction, and off-shore engineering firms. Commercial users of ice related services generally consist of either value-added users or the general public. The value-added user often reformats or integrates government supplied products or data with other information in the construction of tailored products designed to a client's specification. The general public often makes direct application of government supplied products to their individual needs.

JIC products and much of the government data utilized in their construction are or can be made available to commercial users. Presented in this paper are descriptions of JIC ice products, data, available dissemination options, and their appropriate government distribution sources.

2. Products.

Global ice analyses. Global ice conditions

are mapped weekly on a scale of 1:11.6 million for the arctic and 1:16 million for the antarctic. The maps are azimuthal equidistant projections centered at the pole. The smallest homogeneous area resolved by the mapping system is less than (20 km) under best conditions and over (100 km) under the worst. Figure 1 is an example of the weekly Antarctic Ice Analysis.

The mapped features depicted in the ice analyses include classes of ice concentration, classes of ice age, ice edge position, cracks, fractures, leads, and polynyas. In addition, antarctic ice maps contain positions of ice bergs which are greater than 30 km in length. Arctic ice maps contain monthly updated theoretical ice thicknesses at selected arctic stations during seasons of ice growth.

Regional ice analyses. Regional ice analyses are routinely produced for Alaskan waters and the Great Lakes. Figure 2 is an Alaska Region Ice Analysis produced on a 1:8 million scale azimuthal equidistant projection map. Although mapped features for the regional maps are similar to those of the global scale, the larger scale permits a more detailed analysis of ice boundaries and characteristics.

Ice forecasts. Sea ice forecasts differ from ice analyses in that they predict the future state of ice conditions. Ice analyses are often the starting point from which the ablation, formation, or movement of sea ice is predicted. Ice forecasts are produced for various geographical areas in a number of spatial and time scales.

JIC analysis and forecast products are available by mail, facsimile, and alphanumeric messages. Some JIC ice analyses and forecasts are also available through electronic alphanumeric messages. Alphanumeric messages are available in near real time. Table 1 identifies JIC products available by mail and electronic messages. Table 2 identifies products available through NOAA facsimile circuits. Arrangements to receive these products can be made through the identified distribution centers.

3. Methodology

Ice analysis. Sea ice analyses are constructed

TABLE 1. JOINT ICE CENTER (JIC) PRODUCTS AND DISTRIBUTION CENTERS

PRODUCT	FREQUENCY	PRODUCT DESCRIPTION AND FORMAT	DISTRIBUTION CENTER
Arctic Ice Atlas	Yearly	Compilation of weekly operational Eastern and Western Arctic Sea Ice Analyses. Available by mail in hardcopy and microfiche formats.	NTIS
Antarctic Ice Atlas	Bi yearly	Compilation of weekly operational Antarctic Sea Ice Analyses. Available by mail in hardcopy and microfiche formats.	NTIS
JIC Digital Data		JIC Arctic Ice and Antarctic Ice Analyses (1972-1982) in digital format. Available by mail on computer tape.	WDC-A
Eastern Arctic Southern Ice Limit	Weekly	Analysis of arctic sea ice from 95°E westward to 95°W. Hardcopy available by mail.	JIC
Western Arctic Southern Ice Limit	Weekly	Analysis of arctic sea ice from 95°W westward to 95°E. Hardcopy available by mail.	JIC
Antarctic Northern Ice Limit	Weekly	Analysis of antarctic ice conditions. Hardcopy available by mail.	JIC
Great Lakes Ice Analysis	Twice Weekly	Analysis of Great Lakes Ice conditions. Hardcopy available by mail.	SDSD
Southern Ice Limit Eastern and Western Arctic/7 Day Ice Forecast	Weekly	Plain language alphanumeric message of arctic ice conditions. Available through electronic transmissions	NNODDS
30 Day Western Arctic Ice Forecast	Semi-Monthly	30 day arctic sea ice forecast from 95°W westward to 95°E. Hardcopy available by mail.	JIC
30 Day Eastern Arctic Ice Forecast	Semi-Monthly	30 day arctic sea ice forecast from 95°E westward to 95°W. Hardcopy available by mail.	JIC
30 Day Western Ross Sea Ice Forecast	Semi-monthly Dec-Feb	Available only through electronic transmissions.	NNODDS
Western Arctic Seasonal Outlook	Yearly Early May	Predicted opening date of coastal route to Prudhoe Bay and other statistics. Hardcopy available by mail.	JIC
Eastern Arctic Seasonal Outlook	Yearly Early May	Predicted opening dates for Greenland coastal stations and general seasonal ice conditions. Hardcopy available by mail.	JIC
Western Ross Sea and McMurdo Sound Seasonal Outlook	Yearly Early Nov	Predicted seasonal fast ice and general ice conditions. Hardcopy available by mail.	JIC
KEY:			
NTIS	National Technical Information Service 5285 Port Royal Road Alexandria, VA 22314	NNODDS	Navy NOAA Oceanographic Data Distribution System Fleet Numerical Oceanography Center Monterey, CA 93940
WDC-A	World Data Center-A for Glaciology Campus Box 449 Boulder, CO 80309	SDSD	NOAA, NESDIS Satellite Data Services Division World Weather Building, Room 100 Washington, DC 20233
		JIC	Joint Ice Center 4301 Suitland Road Washington, DC 20390

TABLE 2. JOINT ICE CENTER FACSIMILE SCHEDULE

FACSIMILE CIRCUIT	ALASKA REGION ICE ANALYSIS	ANTARCTIC ICE ANALYSIS	30-DAY WESTERN ARCTIC ICE FORECAST	GREAT LAKES ICE ANALYSIS
<u>National</u> ¹ Day Greenwich Mean Time (GMT) Chart Number	Th, Su 11:19 GMT 452			We, Sa 11:19 GMT 452
<u>Digital</u> ¹ Day Greenwich Mean Time (GMT) Chart Number	Th, Su 12:41 GMT 452			We, Sa 12:41 GMT 452
<u>Alaska</u> ¹ Day Greenwich Mean Time (GMT) Chart Number	Mo, We, Fr 21:40 GMT 594		() ² 21:50 GMT 593	
<u>WEFAX</u> ³ <u>GOESWEST</u> Day Greenwich Mean Time (GMT) Chart Number		Daily ⁴ 0235 GMT 0245 GMT GCT1, GCT2		
<u>GOES CENTRAL</u> Day Greenwich Mean Time (GMT) Chart Number		Daily ⁴ 03:25 GMT 03:35 GMT GCT1, GCT2		
<u>NOTES</u>				
<p>1 For acquisition information contact: NOAA, NWS Communications Division/WOTS3 ATTN: User Agreements Contact 8060 13th Street Silver Spring, MD 20910</p> <p>2 Slots are open daily, chart is transmitted twice monthly.</p> <p>3 For acquisition information contact: NOAA, NESDIS ATTN: WEFAX Coordinator World Weather Building Washington, DC 20233</p> <p>4 Chart is updated weekly and transmitted daily in two sections.</p>				

through the integration of all available ice data consisting of both satellite derived and conventional data sources. Satellites provide over 95 percent of the data utilized in a typical global ice analysis. Conventional ice observations although less frequent in number and less extensive in areal extent provide invaluable tie points through which remotely sensed data can be properly interpreted.

Routinely available satellite data consists of imagery from NOAA, DMSP, and NASA satellites. Satellite data is available on either a global or regional basis. Regional availability applies to higher resolution NOAA data which is either received from limited recording capabilities aboard the spacecraft or from a regional receiving station in Fairbanks, Alaska or Wallops Island, Virginia. NOAA and DMSP satellites provide imagery from sensors operating in the visible (VIS) and thermal infrared (IR) bands of the electromagnetic spectrum.

Visible imagery is used to detect ice areas of varying ice types and concentration. The characteristic albedos of the various ice types and water permits the detection of ice and to a degree the relative ages of ice. Ice age discrimination with operationally available NOAA satellite imagery is generally

limited to the age categories of young (10 - 30 cm thickness) and first year (30 - 200 cm) ice. The similar albedo values for new (less than 10 cm) ice and water make discrimination between the two very difficult. Likewise the similar albedo values of first year and old ice (ice surviving at least one summer's melt) with a common snow cover makes discrimination difficult. Only in early October when first year ice has not yet thickened to the first year medium category and prior to significant snowfall does visible imagery provide a reliable discrimination between old and first year ice. The utility of visible imagery is restricted to periods of time containing adequate solar illumination.

The utility of thermal infrared imagery in sea ice detection results from the relative differences in the physical surface temperature of the various ice types and sea surface temperature. These relative surface temperature differences are used to discriminate between various ice types, ice concentrations, and sea surface areas. As with visible imagery the discrimination of ice consisting of various ages is generally limited from young to first year ice. The utility of thermal infrared imagery lessens as the surface temperature contrast between the various ice types and sea surface temperature decreases. During the summer melt period little surface temperature

contrast exists between ice and the sea water in the marginal ice zone. During winter heavy snow cover often inhibits the ability to discriminate between various ice types through image interpretation.

Both visible and thermal infrared sensors are restricted by cloud cover. Climatological mean cloud cover is typically greater than 80 per cent during the summer in the marginal ice zones of many arctic seas, thus greatly inhibiting the utility of these data. Operational visible and infrared imagery is provided in formats with resolutions ranging from 1 to 6 km in resolution. Ice features smaller than the resolution of the various operational formats are integrated into the individual pixels and may not be detected. Hence the greater the resolution of the satellite imagery, the greater the ability to detect various ice features.

Passive microwave imagery processed with NASA's NIMBUS 7 Scanning Multichannel Microwave Radiometer (SMMR) data provides the only all weather, day and night ice detecting sensor. SMMR derived imagery enables the detection of the ice edge on a global spatial scale. Microwave data is used to discriminate between large areas of variable ice concentration or ages. At 18, 21, and 37 GHz the large differences between the emissivities of water and ice types enable the reliable discrimination of ice edge location and polynya location within the ice pack. Only in summer when considerable ice surface melt is present does microwave data present questionable results.

Conventional data consists of aerial ice reconnaissance, ship, and shore observations. Aerial ice reconnaissance data are prepared by JIC ice observers who fly aboard Navy, NOAA, and NASA aircraft. Foreign aerial reconnaissance data is routinely received from the Canadian Atmospheric Environment Service and the Danish government. Additional aerial ice reconnaissance data is provided by U.S. commercial firms. Aerial reconnaissance data generally provides reliable high quality information concerning ice conditions over portions of regional areas such as the north coast of Alaska. Ship and shore ice observations provide point observations along the track of transiting vessels or at coastal land stations.

Conventional observations are generally considered to be highly reliable and are used extensively for ground truthing satellite interpreted data.

Ice Forecasting. The primary objective of the JIC ice forecasting program is to provide ice prediction services in response to user specified temporal and spatial requirements. Existing services include the preparation of the following information:

- (1) short-term ice forecasts for the

ensuing 24 to 96 hour period which provide close tactical support over a specific locality for an ongoing exercise.

- (2) 7-day ice edge forecasts which are prepared weekly and predict ice edge positions on a hemispheric scale,

- (3) 30-day ice forecasts which are produced twice monthly and are used for planning purposes in regional areas where shipping, off-shore construction, or fishing operations are imminent,

- (4) seasonal ice forecasts and outlooks which include forecast periods from 60 to 150 days and are used for long-range strategic planning in regional areas.

Ice forecasting remains a highly subjective endeavor. The ice forecast models, meteorological and oceanographic predictive fields required for the accurate prediction of ice conditions are generally unavailable. The basic classes of operational forecasting techniques are based on empirical/statistical and analogue relationships.

Empirical relationships [1, 2] between the drift of ice and mean sea level surface pressure fields are utilized by NMC and FNOC to produce ice drift forecasts at numerical meteorological model grid point locations in the arctic. Ice drift analyses and forecasts are available in 24 hour time steps through 168 hours.

A theoretical relationship between freezing degree day accumulations and ice thicknesses [3] are utilized by FNOC to provide estimations of ice thicknesses at northern hemispheric land stations bordering ice covered seas. A freezing degree day in Celsius units is the difference between 0°C and the station's below 0°C mean daily surface air temperature.

A statistically derived relationship between meteorological conditions and ice severity index for the Alaskan north slope [4] is utilized in the Western Arctic Seasonal Ice Forecast.

Analogue techniques are used in relating initial ice conditions to predicted ice conditions or predicted meteorological conditions with predicted ice conditions. These techniques are used exclusively in the preparation of 30-Day Ice Forecasts and Seasonal Eastern Arctic and Ross Sea/McMurdo Sound Forecasts.

Background information and all currently utilized ice analysis and forecast procedures including empirical/statistical and analogue techniques are described in the Handbook for Sea Ice Analysis and Forecasting [5].

4. Conclusions.

JIC ice analyses are produced on various time and spatial scales through the integration of conventional and satellite derived data

from NOAA, DMSP, and NASA satellites. Ice forecasts are generated for time periods ranging from 1 day to several months through the employment of statistical/empirical and analogue techniques. JIC products are available to commercial users through the JIC and various U.S. Government distribution centers and communications networks.

5. References

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Figure 1. Joint Ice Center Antarctic Northern Ice Limit Analysis

Figure 2. Joint Ice Center Alaska Region Southern Ice Limit Analysis